

METHODS OF EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A GROUP OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to methods, recommendations and solutions for improving the quality of educational methods in the development of the student team and strengthening the team in the classroom.

Key words: team, members, idea, thought, choice, individual, social, activity, development, education, interest, process, passion, interest, aspiration.

All the reforms carried out in our country are focused on the development of education and the creation of a successful system. An example of this is the new revision of the "Law on Education" on September 23, 2020. The purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of education. Going into the essence of the law, we will explain:

Psinsp is used in the field of education.

Recognition of the priority of education;

Freedom to choose the form of education;

Not allowing discrimination in the field of education;

Provision of equal opportunities for education;

Inculcation of national and universal human values in education and training;

In the field of education, the freedom of education has made it possible for young people to study more widely.

Today's youth are working with teams to further their education.

In order to accelerate the education and knowledge between the

communities, the communities are organizing various events, various courses, conferences, conferences to improve the knowledge of young people, and at the same time, they are finding solutions to their various problems. Here are the researches, activities, in agreement with the teams, each person in the team should work with the youth for education.

It is to gather a youth team that can introduce new things, to include all young people in education, and to ensure employment.

In the modern interpretation, the concept of "community" is used in two different meanings. First of all, a team means an organizational group consisting of several people joining together for a specific goal (for example, a production team, a factory team, an educational team, an economic team, etc.). Second, a team is a highly organized group.

For example, a student body is a highly organized association. Collaborative teams are more productive and motivated toward company goals. Teams with high engagement showed a 21 percent increase in profitability. Teamwork helps everyone communicate better and more often in real time, minimizing friction and delays. All this in turn leads to a high-quality product.

A community (a translation of the Latin word "collectivus", which means a gathering, a mass, a joint meeting, an association, a group) consists of several members (people), a group formed on the basis of a common goal of social importance. means In the Turkic-speaking peoples, including the Uzbeks, the community has always had a social meaning. Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Central Asian thinkers Farobi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi and others justified the need for people to live as a community. Especially the great philosopher-scientist Abu Nasr Farabi in his works emphasizes that the natural tendency to live in a community is the essence of human lifestyle. Farobi expressed the following opinions about this:

The top 7 qualities of a successful team.

- 1) They communicate well with each other.
- 2) They focus on goals and results.
- 3) Everyone contributes.
- 4) They help each other.
- 5) Team members are diverse.
- 6) good leadership.
- 7) They are organized.
- 8) They have fun.

Education in the team and with the help of the team is one of the important principles in the education system. Ideas about the leading role of the team in the formation of the personality were used in the early stages of the development of the science of pedagogy reported. A special form of relationship between its members occurs in the team, which ensures the development of the individual together with the team. But not every group can be considered a team. A community has a number of characteristics that distinguish it from any sufficiently organized group of people.

The student body has important characteristics that make it unique. Below we will talk about the team and its characteristics (signs).

The community is a part of the social society, in which all norms of social life and social relations find their expression. After all, as the community manifests itself in the existing system of relations in the society, mutual unity, cohesion, and connection appear in the goals and aspirations of the community and social society. That is why community life is focused on a clear (unique) goal and acquires a socio-ideological character is considered its leading sign. Each team exists in an integral relationship with other teams. Each member of a certain community participates together with his community in the process of organizing the social activities of the community. To understand the aspirations of the team members, to deeply feel the essence of the goal set before the team, and to be able

to correctly assess its place and role in the formation of the individual. General and private (personal) goals, interests, needs and activities of the team members. shows the unity between.

Used literature

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". - National database of legal documents, No. 06/19/5712/3034, 04/29/2019.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the Concept of Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". <https://lex.uz/docs/4312785>
3. Akramov.F.A. The psychological influence of the primary education teacher on the formation of the child's personality. Modern education/ SOVREMENNOYe OBRAZOVANYe.-2015 - #3-5 p.
4. Mavlyanova R.A. Pakhmankulova N.K. Innovation in primary education (methodical guide). -Tashkent, 2017. -195 p.
5. R. Mavlonva, B. Normurodov, N. Rahmonkulov "Methodology of educational work" -2010